

BMBF-Verbundprojekt:

Erprobung und Anwendung von Kurationskriterien und Qualitätsstandards für audiovisuelle, annotierte Sprachdaten – QUEST.

Teilprojekt *Metadaten* (16QK09B)

Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data

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Data Center for the Humanities
University of Cologne
50923 Cologne
Germany

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[Introduction](#)

[A. Principles](#)

[Use Cases](#)

[Dataset Citation \(Citation\)](#)

[Legal \(Legal\)](#)

[Registering a DOI with DataCite \(DOI\)](#)

[Visibility in General Purpose Search Engines \(Schema.org\)](#)

[Visibility in Open Language Archives Community Catalog \(OLAC\)](#)

[Visibility in the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory \(VLO\)](#)

[Linked Open Data \(LOD\)](#)

[Types of Metadata](#)

[Metadata Licensing](#)

[Standards and Formats](#)

[Modeled Objects](#)

[Recommended Extensions](#)

[Literals, Non-Literals and Language Choice](#)

[Linked Open Data](#)

[Ontologies and Vocabularies](#)

[Properties](#)

[Values](#)

[Surveyed Formats](#)

[DC Elements](#)

[DC Terms](#)

[Schema.org](#)

[DataCite](#)

[DCAT2](#)

[OLAC](#)

[IMDI Element](#)

[Meta Share](#)

[VLO Facets](#)

[HZSK](#)

[IDS \(ADG\)](#)

[TEI Header](#)

[Talkbank/CHILDES](#)

[Wikidata-Property](#)

[B. Recommendations](#)

[Generic Research Data](#)

[Generic \(basic\)](#)

[Identifier](#)

[Title](#)

[Description](#)

[Version](#)

[Keywords – Keyword](#)

[License](#)

[Rightsholder](#)

[Access Rights](#)

[Publication Year](#)

[Publisher](#)

[Creator](#)

[Contributor](#)

[Person](#)

[Name](#)

[Family Name](#)

[Given Name](#)

[Identifier](#)

[Affiliation](#)

[Email](#)

[Organization](#)

[Name](#)

[Identifier](#)

[URL](#)

[Email](#)

[Generic \(extended\)](#)

[sameAs](#)

[isPartOf](#)

[hasPart](#)

[isBasedOn](#)

[Project](#)

[ProjectName](#)

[ProjectDescription](#)

[Language data](#)

[ObjectLanguage](#)

[LinguisticDataType](#)

[Modality](#)

[Language](#)

[Name](#)

[PreferredLabel](#)

[identifier](#)

[Template](#)

[TEMPLATE](#)

[Glossary](#)

Introduction

The *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* provide guidance for assessing the quality and interoperability of metadata for audio-visual language data resources. The recommendations do not specify a particular metadata format nor do they require any particular serialization, as various services and research communities use metadata formats and serialization techniques that are established in their specific field which can differ from established formats in other fields.

Any dataset that provides the information recommended in this document in a formally identifiable and machine-readable way will be considered compliant with these recommendations.

The current document *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* contains the modules Generic Research Data, Language Data, and AV Data that specify recommendations for dataset level metadata for these respective aspects of research data. Metadata relating to other structural units such as data packages – also called session, bundle, or (speech) event – and files as well as metadata relating to more subject specific use cases are not specified in this document.

The key words “MUST”, “MUST NOT”, “REQUIRED”, “SHALL”, “SHALL NOT”, “SHOULD”, “SHOULD NOT”, “RECOMMENDED”, “MAY”, and “OPTIONAL” in this document are to be interpreted as described in [BCP 14 \[RFC2119\]](#) [[RFC8174](#)] when, and only when, they appear in all capitals, as shown here.

A. Principles

The main principles underlying the *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* are the [FAIR principles](#)¹ (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and the concept of Data Maturity (Bahim et al. 2020; FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group 2020). The FAIR principles aim at making digital data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable for humans and machines. The presented metadata recommendations aim to facilitate these principles for audio-visual language data and propagate best practices across communities producing audio-visual language data.

This document formulates recommendations and specifies a set of modular requirements based on specific [use cases](#). Each use case specifies the types of information needed to fulfill one particular function and formalizes the respective requirements for metadata. Any metadata property recommended in this document is motivated by at least one use case.

Findability is addressed by considering the requirements of search portals and data portals such as the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory, Open Language Archives Catalog and Search, as well as Google Dataset Search. The recommendations concerning licensing, access rights as well as referencing with persistent identifiers address **accessibility** and **reusability**. To ensure the greatest possible **interoperability**, the recommendations rely as much as possible on pre-existing well-defined metadata properties from widely used vocabularies. As a consequence, the recommendations utilize properties defined by Dublin Core Terms and Schema.org, FOAF, and SKOS where possible.

The list of recommended metadata properties are intended as a minimal standard supporting a set of specific use cases and facilitating interoperability. Individual metadata formats and vocabularies MAY be more comprehensive and MAY specify any number of additional properties. The section [Recommended Extensions](#) lists vocabularies that SHOULD be used if a metadata format were to be extended to cover the respective thematic areas.

The *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* do not specify a particular metadata format, as a consequence the recommendations identify practical equivalences between properties in relevant formats as a guidance for practitioners as well as for the evaluation of particular metadata sets. Properties may have varying definitions in different formats and may not be equivalent in a strict formal sense. However, the equivalencies identified in this document are based on the fact that the properties are used to express the same or similar value (extensional equivalence) in the various formats. However, the fact that the properties may have differing definitions

¹ Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3(1). 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

in the individual formats should be kept in mind when working with these recommendations. The difference in definition between the formats introduces a level of intensional vagueness that could become relevant in formal application.

Use Cases

Use cases MUST describe well-defined functionalities by referencing published requirements, existing applications and services, or community consensus. The *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* thus reflect existing best practices. Compatibility with these recommendations can serve as a criterion to assess the metadata quality and maturity of a given data set. If you follow these recommendations you can ensure that your data is not only findable in your specific field, but also by a wider research audience using services such as DataCite Commons or Google Dataset Search.

The recommendations in [section B](#) are grouped into modules based on one or more use cases. This keeps compliance with these recommendations modular, while avoiding being overly granular. The module [Generic \(basic\)](#) groups the use cases [DOI](#), [Schema.org](#), [Citation](#) and [Legal](#) together. We consider the Use Cases [DOI](#), [Citation](#), and [Legal](#) essential for any dataset regardless of its data type and scientific background. The requirements of the [Schema.org](#) scenario sit within the scope of this module and are integrated in it. The module [Generic \(extended\)](#) supplements the first module by optional properties from these use cases. The module [Language Data](#) covers the requirements from the use cases concerning the visibility of audio-visual data in the language data-specific search portals [OLAC](#) and [VLO](#).

Dataset Citation (Citation)

In order to be citable, a dataset must provide properties that facilitate the generation of a citation following established data citation formats.

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST provide properties that conform with the [Force11 joint declaration of data citation principles](#) (Martone 2014).

Legal (Legal)

In order to be (re-)usable, a dataset must provide legal information in a standardized, machine readable way.

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST provide licensing information in a machine readable format. The license information must include a HTTP URI that unambiguously identifies a specific version of the license used.

If the dataset is not provided under an open license, the metadata MUST provide means to contact the rights holder in order to gain usage rights or otherwise unambiguously specify a method to gain usage rights.

Registering a DOI with DataCite (DOI)

In order to create a new DOI through DataCite, the user has to submit a metadata description following the DataCite Metadata Schema.

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST supply both *mandatory* and *recommended* DataCite properties, as specified by the [DataCite Metadata Schema 4.4](#).

Visibility in General Purpose Search Engines (Schema.org)

[Schema.org](#) with its type [Dataset](#) offers a way to embed dataset related metadata directly into webpages and make it accessible through HTTP. Schema.org specifies three possible methods for embedding structured data in HTML: Microdata, RDFa, and JSON-LD.

By embedding metadata in a publicly available webpage, the metadata are made accessible to any search engine that can parse Schema.org structured data. At the moment, this includes at least Google, Bing, Yahoo!, and Yandex. With [Google Dataset Search](#), Google is the only general purpose search engine that currently offers a service specifically optimized for dataset search. In order to be discoverable through Google Dataset Search, the data provider has to provide metadata following either the Schema.org vocabulary or DCAT, serialized as JSON-LD or alternatively as RDFa. The *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* follow Google in recommending Schema.org serialized as JSON-LD as the best practice for providing metadata as structured data on the World Wide Web.

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST supply the *required* and *recommended* Schema.org properties as specified by the [Google structured data guidelines for datasets](#).

Visibility in Open Language Archives Community Catalog (OLAC)

In order to be discoverable through the [Open Language Archives Community Catalog](#) (OLAC) the data provider must provide metadata following the [OLAC Metadata standard](#).

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST provide metadata properties as required and recommended by the OLAC Metadata standard.

Visibility in the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)

In order to be discoverable through the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), the data provider must provide metadata in CMDI format following the [VLO guidelines](#).

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST provide metadata properties as required and recommended by the VLO guidelines and identify these properties through links to appropriate concepts in the [CLARIN Concept Registry](#).

Linked Open Data (LOD)

Metadata sets should follow [linked open data best practices](#). The metadata should reference other resources and vocabularies, use URIs as names for things and use HTTP URIs, where possible, so that people can look up those names.

To satisfy this use case, a metadata set MUST provide HTTP URIs to identify objects in addition to (or where possible alternative to) literal values and SHOULD reference well established ontologies or vocabularies.

Types of Metadata

The *Metadata Recommendations* cover dataset level catalog metadata. This includes basic descriptive, structural and administrative metadata. In particular, information that is required to facilitate findability and general (re-)usability of resources.

Information closely related to the research process such as contextual metadata and paradata is not covered by this recommendation. Information required for internal administrative purposes including specific administrative metadata and preservation metadata are also not covered by these recommendations.

Metadata Licensing

Metadata documents and databases might be covered by copyright in some jurisdictions. Copyrighted and restrictively licensed metadata can be a severe impediment to availability, interoperability, and reuse. Even if no copyright is claimed or cannot be claimed, the remaining uncertainty about the legal status of the metadata can be an obstacle to use and reuse of the information.

The **recommendation for metadata licensing** is to eliminate any uncertainties about the legal status of the metadata and explicitly license them as [Creative Commons Zero 1.0 Universal \(CC0 1.0\) Public Domain Dedication](#).

Standards and Formats

The *Metadata Recommendations* rely on established standards and open formats where possible. The following standards and formats are currently referenced or used in this document.

ISO 8601-1, *Date and time — Representations for information interchange — Part 1: Basic rules*. URL: <https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html>

ISO 6709:2008, *Standard representation of geographic point location by coordinates*. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/39242.html>

ISO 639-3:2007 *Codes for the representation of names of languages — Part 3: Alpha-3 code for comprehensive coverage of languages*. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/39534.html>

ISO 26324:2012 *Information and documentation — Digital object identifier system*. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/43506.html>

ISO 27729:2012 *Information and documentation — International standard name identifier (ISNI)*. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/44292.html>

MIME *MIME Internet Media Types*. URL: <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

RFC 3986 *Uniform Resource Identifier (URI): Generic Syntax*. URL: <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3986>

JSON-LD 1.1 *JSON-LD 1.1 A JSON-based Serialization for Linked Data*. URL: <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/>

RDFa 1.1 *RDFa 1.1 Primer – Third Edition Rich Structured Data Markup for Web Documents*. URL: <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdfa-primer/>

RDF Schema 1.1 *RDF Schema 1.1*. URL: <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

W3C *Personal names around the world*. URL: <https://www.w3.org/International/questions/qa-personal-names>

Modeled Objects

The *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* utilize several abstract objects to describe audio-visual language data. The **dataset** – also called corpus or collection in language related research data – represents a set of data that are grouped into a unit according to one or more scientifically relevant properties. A dataset SHOULD contain one or more data packages or one or more files. A **data package** is an abstract object that groups one or more files. In the context of audio-visual language data, a data package often contains data representing a single speech event as well as supplementary information relating to this event. Depending on the community, this object is variously called *session*, *bundle*, or (*speech*) *event*. For audio-visual language data, a data package contains one or more media files and optionally files containing often time-aligned annotations as well as other files containing different types of annotations or additional information. The **file** is a relevant structural unit of research data and corresponds to the computer file on a storage device. Dataset or data package metadata SHOULD reference files with persistent identifiers. While the file is a relevant object in this document, the *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* do not specify file-level metadata. Metadata related to file format and file properties SHOULD be integrated into the file itself. Several AV container formats allow the integration of metadata in the header of the file. Alternatively or additionally, file specific metadata MAY be stored in a sidecar file.

Additionally, *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data* model **person**, **organization**, and **language** as complex objects relevant for dataset and data package metadata. These objects are contained in dataset and data package level metadata.

Metadata describing a **data catalog** are not covered by the *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data*. A recommendation for modeling data catalogs is given in the next section.

Recommended Extensions

This section lists recommendations for metadata types or metadata objects not covered by the *Metadata Recommendations for Audio-Visual Language Data*. The following formats SHOULD be used to extend the set of metadata properties given in this document.

Data Catalogs: [DCAT](#) (Version 2)
Media Files: [XMP](#), ISO [16684-1:2019 part 1](#), ISO [16684-2:2014 part 2](#)
Provenance: W3C [PROV](#) set of recommended standards
Preservation: PREMIS Data Dictionary, [Version 3.0](#)
Actors/Participants: [FOAF](#)

Literals, Non-Literals and Language Choice

Metadata can contain literals as well as non-literal. In digital metadata, literals are strings representing natural language words or phrases. Non-literals are identifiers and in the context of digital metadata URIs. In general, values SHOULD use and reference existing FAIR vocabularies.

The metadata MUST provide the basic information as literals. In this way, the information is independent from external services and remains self-sufficiently human-readable. Literal values are crucial to making resources resilient, self-contained objects that can withstand changes to the surrounding data infrastructure.

Non-literal SHOULD be URI and in particular HTTP URIs. Non-literals are a crucial part of any linked data infrastructure and SHOULD be included in the metadata, generously. However, non-literal SHOULD reference sustainable resources to ensure that the HTTP URIs remain resolvable over a long time.

Literals MUST be provided in an appropriate language, widely used in the intended audience. To ensure global findability and (re-)usability literals SHOULD be provided in English, at least additionally. Metadata MAY contain values in any number of languages.

Linked Open Data

Metadata quality can be increased by the use of non-literals and controlled vocabularies. When referencing the values from controlled vocabularies using resolvable HTTP URIs and other Web standards will increase the usefulness of the metadata.

The recommendation for linking metadata is to reference external controlled vocabularies where feasible and to use resolvable URIs when possible. This SHOULD be implemented as additional information accompanying literal metadata values. Metadata formats and data providers are free in how to provide additional non-literals. If an exclusively Linked Open Data infrastructure is addressed, metadata containing non-literal HTTP URIs MAY be published alternatively to providing literals.

Ontologies and Vocabularies

Well-defined stable ontologies and vocabularies for metadata properties and values are crucial to ensure interoperability of the data. The re-use of established ontologies and vocabularies allows for the conversion between metadata formats and conformance with other standards. The *Metadata Recommendations* use the ontologies and vocabularies listed in the section [Properties](#) to define its metadata properties. The *Metadata Recommendations* endorse the use of references to vocabularies as values. The recommended vocabularies are given in section [Values](#).

Properties

	prefix	namespace
DC Elements 1.1	dc	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/
DC Terms	dcterms	http://purl.org/dc/terms/
OLAC	olac	http://www.language-archives.org/OLAC/1.1/
Schema.org	sdo	https://schema.org/
FOAF	foaf	http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/
SKOS	skos	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#

The *Metadata Recommendations* prefer the usage of DC Terms properties over DC Elements properties. However, DC Elements 1.1 is standardized as ISO Standard [15836-1:2017](#), IETF [RFC 5013](#) and NISO Standard [Z39.85](#). If compliance with these standards is important for a use case the relevant properties can be defined as DC Elements 1.1 instead.

Values

	prefix	namespace
ORCID	orcid	https://orcid.org/
ISNI	isni	http://isni.org/isni/

ROR	ror	https://ror.org/
Wikidata	wd	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/
Glottolog	glott	https://glottolog.org/resource/languoid/id/
ISO 639-3	iso639-3	https://iso639-3.sil.org/code/
GeoNames	gn	http://sws.geonames.org/

Surveyed Formats

DC Elements

<https://dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

DC Terms

<http://purl.org/dc/terms>

Schema.org

<https://schema.org/>

DataCite

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

DCAT2

<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

OLAC

<http://www.language-archives.org/OLAC/metadata.html>

IMDI Element

IMDI (ISLE Metadata Initiative) PART 1: Metadata Elements for Session Descriptions Version 3.0.4. 2003. (retrieved from https://www.mpi.nl/IMDI/documents/Proposals/IMDI_MetaData_3.0.4.pdf, archived version)

Meta Share

http://www.meta-share.org/assets/pdf/META-SHARE_Documentation_v3.1.pdf

VLO Facets

<https://vlo.clarin.eu/search?1>

HZSK

https://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry/#/?itemId=clarin.eu:cr1:p_1427452477080®istrySpace=published

IDS (ADG)

http://agd.ids-mannheim.de/download/metadaten_schemata_DGD_2.0_2009-09-01.pdf

TEI Header

<https://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/ref-teiHeader.html>

Talkbank/CHILDES

CHILDES was established in 1984 as a corpus for first language acquisition data. It belongs to the [TalkBank](#) system. TalkBank includes various corpora for studying conversational interactions.

https://talkbank.org/manuals/CHAT.html#_Toc40195866

[CHAT](#) (for data package objects)

Wikidata-Property

<https://www.wikidata.org/>

B. Recommendations

Generic Research Data

The module for generic research data contains metadata properties applicable for all types of research data.

Generic (basic)

Use cases: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal, LOD

Property	URI	Optionality
identifier	dcterms:identifier	REQUIRED

title	dcterms:title	REQUIRED
description	dcterms:description	REQUIRED
version	sdo:version	RECOMMENDED
keywords	sdo:keywords	RECOMMENDED
license	dcterms:license	REQUIRED
rightsholder	dcterms:rightsholder	RECOMMENDED
accessRights	dcterms:accessRights	OPTIONAL
publicationYear	sdo:datePublished	REQUIRED
publisher	dcterms:publisher	REQUIRED
creator	dcterms:creator	REQUIRED
contributor	dcterms:contributor	RECOMMENDED

Identifier

Label: identifier

URI: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/identifier>

Definition: An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.

Comment: We recommend using Handle or DOI as HTTP URIs. DataCite requires a DOI identifier and the CLARIN VLO expects a Handle PID.

Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, VLO

Vocabulary: recommended DOI or Handle

Value scheme: anyURI (HTTP URIs)

Obligation: REQUIRED

Occurrences: 1 - unbounded

ConceptLink: [persistent identifier](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [identifier](#)

DC Terms: [identifier](#)

Schema.org: [Identifier](#) (recommended)

DataCite: Identifier (obligatory) – only doi PIDs

TEI-Header: @xml:id (global attribute)

DCAT2: [dcterms:identifier](#)

OLAC: [dc:identifier](#)

IMDI Element: //METATRANSCRIPT/@ArchiveHandle

Meta Share: //resourceInfo/identificationInfo/metaShareId or identifier

VLO Facet: id
 HZSK: PID
 IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/@Kennung
 CHILDES: CMDI_PID and Identifier
 Wikidata-Property: —

Title

Label: Title
URI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/title>
Definition: A name given to the resource.
Comment: We recommend human-readable names.
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, citation

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: string
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 - unbounded
ConceptLink: [title](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [title](#)
 DC Terms: [title](#)
 Schema.org: [name](#) [GDS: obligatory]
 DataCite: Title [obligatory]
 TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/title
 DCAT2: [dcterms:title](#)
 OLAC: [dcterms:title](#)
 IMDI Element: //Session/Title or Name
 Meta Share: //resource/Info/identificationInfo/resourceName
 VLO Facet: name
 HZSK: Name
 IDS (ADG): —
 CHILDES: Title
 Wikidata-Property: title ([P1476](#))

Description

Label: description
URI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/description>
Definition: An account of the resource.
Comment: A free-text account of the item.
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: string

Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 - unbounded
ConceptLink: [description](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DCMI: Description
 Schema.org: [description \(https://schema.org/description\)](https://schema.org/description) [obligatory]
 DataCite: Description [recommended]
 TEI-Header: //fileDesc/sourceDesc
 DCAT2: dcterms:description (<http://purl.org/dc/terms/description>)
 OLAC: Description
 IMDI Element: //Session/Description
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/identificationInfo/description
 VLO Facet: description
 HZSK: Description
 IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Basisdaten/Beschreibung
 CHILDES: Description
 Wikidata-Property: —

Version

Label: version
URI: <https://schema.org/version>
Definition: The version number of the resource. (DataCite)
 The version of the [CreativeWork](#) embodied by a specified resource. (Schema.org)
Comment: —
Use Case: GDS/Schema.org, citation

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: string
Obligation: OPTIONAL
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: [version](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
 DC Terms: —
 Schema.org: [version](#) [GDS: recommended]
 DataCite: version [optional]
 TEI-Header: //fileDesc/appInfo/application/@version or
 //fileDesc/editionStmt/edition
 DCAT2: —
 OLAC: —
 IMDI Element: //METATRANSCRIPT/Version
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/versionInfo/version

VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	Version
IDS (ADG):	//Ereignis/@Kennung [part of the identifier]
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	[software version identifier (P348)]

Keywords – Keyword

Label:	keywords
URI:	https://schema.org/keywords
Definition:	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.
Comment:	text, Controlled Vocabulary, HTTP URI
Use Case:	DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org

Vocabulary:	Wikidata
Value scheme:	text or for LOD use case anyURI (HTTP URIs)
Obligation:	RECOMMENDED
Occurrences:	0 – 1
ConceptLink:	metadata tag

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	≈ subject
DC Terms:	≈ subject
Schema.org:	keywords [GDS: recommended]
DataCite:	Subject [recommended]
TEI-Header:	//profileDesc/textClass/keywords
DCAT2:	dcat:keyword
OLAC:	≈ dc:subject
IMDI Element:	(Session/Keys or Session/Content/Keys)
Meta Share:	//documentInfo/keywords
VLO Facet:	Keywords
HZSK:	Keys
IDS (ADG):	//Korpus/Deskriptoren
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	≈ main subject (P921)

License

Label:	license
URI:	http://purl.org/dc/terms/license
Definition:	A legal document giving official permission to do something with a resource.
Comment:	HTTP URI
Use Case:	GDS/Schema.org, Legal, LOD

Vocabulary: <https://spdx.org/licenses/> (RECOMMENDED)
Value scheme: anyURI (HTTP URIs) [alternatively: text]
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – 1
ConceptLink: [license](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: [license](#)
Schema.org: [license](#) [GDS: recommended]
DataCite: rightsURI [optional]
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/publicationStmt/availability/license
DCAT2: [dcterms:license](#)
OLAC: [dcterms:license](#) (as a refinement to Rights)
IMDI Element: //Session/Access/Description
Meta Share: //resourceInfo/distributionInfo/licence
VLO Facet: license
HZSK: License
IDS (ADG): //Sprecher/Rechteverwaltung/Nutzungsrechte
//Korpus/Quellenaufnahmen/Archivierung/Nutzungsrechte
CHILDES: Rights
Wikidata-Property: copyright license ([P275](#))

Rightsholder

Label: rightsHolder
URI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder>
Definition: A person or organization owning or managing rights over the resource.
Comment: —
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, Legal, OLAC, VLO,

Vocabulary:

Value scheme: text, component *person or organization*
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: [Legal Owner](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: [rightsHolder](#)
Schema.org: [copyrightHolder](#) [GDS: —]
DataCite: contributor (type:RightsHolder) [recommended]
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/publicationStmt/authority
DCAT2: —
OLAC: —
IMDI Element: //Session/Access/Owner

Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/distributionInfo/distributionRightsHolder or //resourceInfo/distributionInfo/iprHolder
VLO Facet:	rightsHolder
HZSK:	LegalOwner
IDS (ADG):	//Sprecher/Rechteverwaltung
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	—

Access Rights

Label:	accessRights
URI:	http://purl.org/dc/terms/accessRights
Definition:	Information about who has access to the resource or an indication of its security status.
Comment:	—
Use Case:	Legal, LangDoc

Vocabulary:	N/A
Value scheme:	text
Obligation:	OPTIONAL
Occurrences:	0 – 1
ConceptLink:	availability

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	Access Rights
Schema.org:	≈ conditionsOfAccess [GDS: —]
DataCite:	—
TEI-Header:	//fileDesc/publicationStmt/availability
DCAT2:	dcterms:accessRights
OLAC:	dcterms:accessRights (as a refinement to Rights)
IMDI Element:	//Session/Access/Availability
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/distributionInfo/availability
VLO Facet:	Availability
HZSK:	DistributionType
IDS (ADG):	//Ereignis/Quellenaufnahme/Distribution
CHILDES:	IMDI_AccessAvailability
Wikidata-Property:	access status (P6954) or access restriction status (P7228)

Publication Year

Label:	publicationYear
URI:	https://schema.org/datePublished
Definition:	Date of first broadcast/publication.
Comment:	—

Use Case: DOI/DataCite, Citation

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: date
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – 1
ConceptLink: [Year of Publication](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: — ([date](#))
DC Terms: ≈ [dateCopyrighted](#) / [issued](#)
Schema.org: [datePublished](#) [GDS: —]
DataCite: PublicationYear [obligatory]
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/publicationStmt/date
DCAT2: [dcterms:issued](#)
OLAC: [dcterms:dateCopyrighted](#) / [dcterms:issued](#)
IMDI Element: //Session/Date
Meta Share: //documentInfo/year or
//resourceInfo/distributionInfo/availabilityStartDate
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: PublicationDate
IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/@in_DGD_seit
CHILDES: Date
Wikidata-Property: publication date ([P577](#))

Publisher

Label: publisher
URI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/publisher>
Definition: An entity responsible for making the resource available.
Comment: —
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, Citation, OLAC, VLO, LOD

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: component *person or organization* (LOD: anyURI)
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [publisher](#)
DC Terms: [publisher](#)
Schema.org: [publisher](#) [GDS: —]
DataCite: Publisher [mandatory]
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/publicationStmt/publisher
DCAT2: [dcterms:publisher](#)

OLAC: [dc:publisher](#)
 IMDI Element: //Session/Access/Publisher
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/documentInfo/publisher
 VLO Facet: Collection
 HZSK: —
 IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Quellenaufnahme/Archivierung or Distribution/@Stelle
 CHILDES: Publisher
 Wikidata-Property: publisher ([P123](#))

Creator

Label: creator
URI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator>
<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/maker>
Definition: An entity responsible for making the resource.
Comment: —
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal, OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary: —
Value scheme: component, text
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – unbounded
ConceptLink: [creator](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [creator](#)
 DC Terms: [creator](#)
 Schema.org: [creator](#) [GDS: recommended]
 DataCite: Creator [mandatory]
 TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/author
 DCAT2: [dcterms:creator](#)
 OLAC: [dc:creator](#)
 IMDI Element: (//Session//Actors/Actor/Role[text()="Author" or text()="Researcher"])
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/resourceCreationInfo/resourceCreator or
 //resourceInfo/documentInfo/author
 VLO Facet: —
 HZSK: Creator
 IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Projekt/Personal
 CHILDES: Creator
 Wikidata-Property: creator ([P170](#))

Contributor

Label: contributor

URI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/contributor>
Definition: An entity responsible for making contributions to the resource.
Comment: —
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, Legal, OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary: —
Value scheme: component, text
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – unbounded
ConceptLink: [contributor](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [contributor](#)
DC Terms: [contributor](#)
DataCite: Contributor [optional]
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt
DCAT2: [dcterms:contributor](#)
OLAC: contributor
IMDI Element: (//Session/Actors/Actor/Role/Contributor)
Meta Share: //resourceInfo/actorInfo or //resourceInfo/personSourceSetInfo
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: Contributor
IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Projekt/Personal/An_E_teilnehmende_Forscher
//Ereignis/Projekt/Personal/An_E_teilnehmende_Techniker
CHILDES: Contributor
Wikidata-Property: contributor to the creative work or subject ([P767](#))

Person

The type *person* is a representation of the most relevant properties of an individual. The property *name* is intended for legacy formats that do not provide a segmented name. While the segmentation into *Family Name* and *Given Name* is culturally highly problematic. Driven by the need to produce a structure name information for citation and sorting. This is required by the function of giving attribution to the dataset creators following the Data Citation Principles. The recommended data structure of *familyName* and *givenName* will not be adequate for many cultural naming systems, but it reproduces the manner of how names are treated in bibliographical and citational contexts, while remaining compatible with existing formats. If it should be necessary for a project to differ from these conventions, instructions should be added to ensure formats are being used correctly. The property *name* can be used to record the full name in its proper unsegmented sequential order.

The type *person* is used in the context of the type *creator* and *contributor*. *Person* is thus used for attribution. The bibliographical context is the relevant functional context for

the type *person*. Alternatively to the type defined here, the more extensive types Schema.org *person* ([sdo:person](https://schema.org/person)) or FOAF *person* ([foaf:person](http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/person)) can be used.

For citation, the segmentation of names and labels for these segments were chosen following [W3C Personal names around the world](#).

Property	URI	Optionality
name	sdo:name foaf:name	OPTIONAL
familyName	sdo:familyName foaf:familyName	REQUIRED
givenName	sdo:givenName foaf:givenName	RECOMMENDED
identifier	sdo:identifier	REQUIRED
affiliation	sdo:affiliation	RECOMMENDED
email	sdo:email	RECOMMENDED

Name

Label: name

URI: <https://schema.org/name>
<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/name>

Definition: The name of the item.

Comment: see also *W3C Personal names around the world*.

Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal, OLAC, VLO, LangDoc

Vocabulary: N/A

Value scheme: text

Obligation: OPTIONAL

Occurrences: 0 – 1

ConceptLink: [name](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —

DC Terms: —

Schema.org: [name](#) [GDS: —]

DataCite: creatorName / contributorName [mandatory]

TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/author/name

DCAT2: [foaf:name](#)

OLAC: —

IMDI Element: //Session/Actors/Actor/FullName

Meta Share: —
 VLO Facet: —
 HZSK: Person
 IDS (ADG): (//Ereignis/Projekt/Personal/An_E_teilnehmende_Forscher,
 An_E_teilnehmende_Techniker)
 CHILDES: —
 Wikidata-Property: name ([P2561](#))

Family Name

Label: familyName
URI: <https://schema.org/familyName>
Definition: In some cultures, a surname, family name, or last name is the portion of one's personal name that indicates one's family, tribe or community.
Comment: Schema.org definition: "Family name. In the U.S., the last name of a Person. This can be used along with givenName instead of the name Property." See also *W3C Personal names around the world*.
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, Citation

Vocabulary: —
Value scheme: text
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
 DC Terms: —
 Schema.org: [familyName](#) [GDS:—]
 DataCite: familyName [optional]
 TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/author/name/surname
 DCAT2: (foaf:familyName)
 OLAC: —
 IMDI Element: —
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/personInfo/surname
 VLO Facet: —
 HZSK: —
 IDS (ADG): —
 CHILDES: —
 Wikidata-Property: family name ([P734](#))

Given Name

Label: givenName
URI: <https://schema.org/givenName>

Definition: The part of a personal name that identifies a person, potentially with a middle name as well, and differentiates that person from the other members of a group (typically a family or clan) who have a common surname.

Comment: Schema.org definition: "Given name. In the U.S., the first name of a Person. This can be used along with familyName instead of the name property." See also *W3C Personal names around the world*.

Use Case: DOI/DataCite, Citation

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: text
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
 DC Terms: —
 Schema.org: [givenName](#) [GDS:—]
 DataCite: givenName [optional]
 TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/author/name/forename
 DCAT2: (foaf:givenName)
 OLAC: —
 IMDI Element: —
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/personInfo/givenName
 VLO Facet: —
 HZSK: —
 IDS (ADG): —
 CHILDES: —
 Wikidata-Property: given name ([P735](#))

Identifier

Label: identifier
URI: <https://schema.org/identifier>
Definition: Refined as person identifier
Comment: Schema.org definition: "The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of Thing."
Use Case: DOI/DataCite

Vocabulary: ORCID, ISNI, Wikidata, (fallback: email, MAILTO URIs)
Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – unbounded
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	—
Schema.org:	identifier
DataCite:	nameIdentifier
TEI-Header:	//fileDesc/titleStmt/author/idno
DCAT2:	foaf:accountName
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	—
Meta Share:	—
VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	—
IDS (ADG):	—
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	ORCID iD (P496), ISNI (P213), email address (P968)

Affiliation

Label:	affiliation
URI:	https://schema.org/affiliation
Definition:	An organization that this person is affiliated with.
Comment:	—
Use Case:	DOI/DataCite

Vocabulary:	N/A
Value scheme:	component, text, anyURI
Obligation:	REQUIRED/RECOMMENDED/OPTIONAL
Occurrences:	0 – unbounded
ConceptLink:	—

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	—
Schema.org:	affiliation [GDS: —]
DataCite:	affiliation [optional]
TEI-Header:	//fileDesc/titleStmt/author/affiliation
DCAT2:	foaf:workplaceHomepage
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	//Session/Actors/Actor/Contact/Organization
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/personInfo/affiliation
VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	Organisation
IDS (ADG):	—
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	affiliation (P1416)

Email

Label:	email
URI:	https://schema.org/email
Definition:	Email address.
Comment:	—
Use Case:	Legal
Vocabulary:	N/A
Value scheme:	text, anyURI (mailto URI)
Obligation:	RECOMMENDED (REQUIRED for rightsholder)
Occurrences:	0 – unbounded
ConceptLink:	—

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	—
Schema.org:	email [GDS:—]
DataCite:	—
TEI-Header:	//fileDesc/titleStmt/author/email
DCAT2:	foaf:mbox
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	//Session/Actors/Actor/Contact/Email
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/personInfo/communicationInfo/email
VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	Contact
IDS (ADG):	//Ereignis/Quellenaufnahme/Distribution/Kontakt
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	email address (P968)

Organization

The type *organization* is a representation of the most relevant properties of an organization. The type *organization* is used in the context of the type publisher and rightsHolder. Alternatively to the type defined here, the more extensive types Schema.org organization ([sdo:organization](#)) can be used.

Property	URI	Optionality
name	sdo:name	REQUIRED
identifier	sdo:identifier	RECOMMENDED
URL	sdo:url	RECOMMENDED

email	sdo:email	RECOMMENDED
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Name

Label: name
URI: <https://schema.org/name>
Definition: The name of the item.
Comment: —
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: text
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: —
Schema.org: [name](#) [GDS: —]
DataCite: creatorName / contributorName [mandatory]
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/resp
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/name
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/orgName
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/persName
DCAT2: [foaf:name](#)
OLAC: —
IMDI Element: —
Meta Share: //resourceInfo/organizationInfo/organizationName
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: —
IDS (ADG): —
CHILDES: —
Wikidata-Property: official name ([P1448](#))

Identifier

Label: identifier
URI: <https://schema.org/identifier>
Definition: Refined as organization identifier
Comment: Schema.org definition: “The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of Thing.”
Use Case: DOI/DataCite

Vocabulary: GRID, ROR, ISNI, Wikidata

Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – unbounded
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: —
Schema.org: [identifier](#)
DataCite: affiliationIdentifier
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/resp/idno
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/orgName/idno
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/persName/idno
DCAT2: —
OLAC: —
IMDI Element: —
Meta Share: —
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: —
IDS (ADG): —
CHILDES: —
Wikidata-Property: GRID ([P2427](#)), ROR ([P6782](#)), ISNI ([P213](#))

URL

Label: url
URI: <https://schema.org/url>
Definition: URL of the item.
Comment: —
Use Case: GDS/Schema.org

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: —
Schema.org: [sdo:url](#) [GDS:—]
DataCite: —
TEI-Header: //fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/resp/idno
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/orgName/idno
//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/persName/idno
DCAT2: [foaf:homepage](#)

OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	—
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/organizationInfo/communicationInfo/url
VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	—
IDS (ADG):	—
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	official website (P859)

Email

Label:	email
URI:	https://schema.org/email
Definition:	Email address.
Comment:	—
Use Case:	Legal
Vocabulary:	N/A
Value scheme:	text, anyURI (mailto URI)
Obligation:	RECOMMENDED (REQUIRED for rightsholder)
Occurrences:	0 – 1
ConceptLink:	—

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	—
Schema.org:	email [GDS:—]
DataCite:	—
TEI-Header:	//fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/resp/email //fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/orgName/email //fileDesc/titleStmt/respStmt/persName/email
DCAT2:	foaf:mbx
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	//Session/Contact/Email
VLO Facet:	—
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/organizationInfo/communicationInfo/email
HZSK:	Contact
IDS (ADG):	//Ereignis/Quellenaufnahme/Distribution/Kontakt
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	email address (P968)

Generic (extended)

Use cases: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org

Property	URI	Optionality
sameAs	sdo:sameAs skos:exactMatch	OPTIONAL
isPartOf	sdo:isPartOf dcterms:isPartOf	OPTIONAL
hasPart	sdo:hasPart dcterms:hasPart	OPTIONAL
isBasedOn	sdo:isBasedOn dcterms:isVersionOf	OPTIONAL
Project	quest:organization sdo:Organization sdo:Project	OPTIONAL

sameAs

Label: sameAs

URI: <https://schema.org/sameAs>

Definition: Indicates that A is identical to B (DataCite)

Comment: Schema.org definition: "URL of a reference Web page that unambiguously indicates the item's identity. E.g. the URL of the item's Wikipedia page, Wikidata entry, or official website."

Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, LOD

Vocabulary: N/A

Value scheme: anyURI

Obligation: OPTIONAL

Occurrences: 0 – unbounded

ConceptLink: [identity relation](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [\(relation\)](#)

DC Terms: [\(relation\)](#)

Schema.org: [sameAs](#) [GDS:recommended]

DataCite: IsIdenticalTo [recommended]

TEI-Header: @sameAs (global linking)

DCAT2: owl:sameAs

OLAC: —

IMDI Element: //Session/Resources/Source/ResourceRef

Meta Share: //resourceInfo/relationInfo/relationType/relatedResource

VLO Facet: —

HZSK: —

IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme

//Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_SE
 //Ereignis/Transkript/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahme
 //Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme,
 Relation_zu_Sprechereignissen
 //Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Transkripte/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahmen
 CHILDES: Relation
 Wikidata-Property: exact match ([P2888](#))

isPartOf

Label: isPartOf
URI: <https://schema.org/isPartOf>
Definition: A related resource in which the described resource is physically or logically included. (Definition of dcterms:isPartOf)
Comment: Schema.org definition: "Indicates an item or CreativeWork that this item, or CreativeWork (in some sense), is part of."
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, OLAC, LOD

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: OPTIONAL
Occurrences: 0 – unbounded
ConceptLink: [holonym part synset relation](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
 DC Terms: [isPartOf](#)
 Schema.org: [isPartOf](#) [GDS:recommended]
 DataCite: isPartOf [recommended]
 TEI-Header: —
 DCAT2: [dcterms:isPartOf](#)
 OLAC: dc:relation isPartOf DC-Q
 IMDI Element: —
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/relationInfo/relationType/relatedResource
 VLO Facet: —
 HZSK: —
 IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme
 //Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_SE
 //Ereignis/Transkript/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahme
 //Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme,
 Relation_zu_Sprechereignissen
 //Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Transkripte/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahmen
 CHILDES: Relation
 Wikidata-Property: part of ([P361](#))

hasPart

Label: hasPart
URI: <https://schema.org/hasPart>
Definition: A related resource that is included either physically or logically in the described resource. (dcterms:hasPart)
Comment: Schema.org definition: "Indicates an item or CreativeWork that is part of this item, or CreativeWork (in some sense)."
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, OLAC, LOD

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: OPTIONAL
Occurrences: 0 – unbounded
ConceptLink: [meronym part synset relation](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: [dcterms:hasPart](#)
Schema.org: [hasPart](#) [GDS:recommended]
DataCite: hasPart [recommended]
TEI-Header: —
DCAT2: [dcterms:hasPart](#)
OLAC: dc:relation hasPart DC-Q
IMDI Element: —
Meta Share: //resourceInfo/relationInfo/relationType/relatedResource
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: —
IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme
//Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_SE
//Ereignis/Transkript/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahme
//Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme,
Relation_zu_Sprechereignissen
//Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Transkripte/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahmen
CHILDES: Relation
Wikidata-Property: has part ([P527](#))

isBasedOn

Label: isBasedOn
URI: <https://schema.org/isBasedOn>
Definition: A related resource of which the described resource is a version, edition, or adaptation. (dcterms:isVersionOf)
Comment: Schema.org definition: "A resource from which this work is derived or from which it is a modification or adaption."
Use Case: DOI/DataCite, GDS/Schema.org, OLAC, LOD

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: OPTIONAL
Occurrences: 0 – unbounded
ConceptLink: [source description](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: [dcterms:isVersionOf](#)
Schema.org: [isBasedOn](#) [GDS:recommended]
DataCite: ≈ isDerivedFrom [recommended]
TEI-Header: @source (global linking)
DCAT2: [dcterms:isVersionOf](#)
OLAC: dc:relation isVersionOf
IMDI Element: //Session/Resources/Source/ResourceRef
Meta Share: //resourceInfo/relationInfo/relationType/relatedResource
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: OriginalSource
IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme
//Ereignis/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_SE
//Ereignis/Transkript/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahme
//Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Basisdaten/Relation_zu_Quellenaufnahme,
Relation_zu_Sprechereignissen
//Korpus/SE-Aufnahme/Transkripte/Relation_zu_SE-Aufnahmen
CHILDES: Relation
Wikidata-Property: based on ([P144](#))

Project

Label: Project
URI: <https://schema.org/Project>
Definition: An enterprise (potentially individual but typically collaborative), planned to achieve a particular aim.
Comment: —
Use Case: GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal, OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: text
Obligation: OPTIONAL
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: [project name](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: —

Schema.org:	sdo:project [GDS:—]
DataCite:	—
DCAT2:	prov:wasGeneratedBy
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	//Session/Project
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/projectInfo
VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	Project
IDS (ADG):	//Ereignis/Projekt
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	project (Q170584)

ProjectName

Label:	ProjectName
URI:	https://schema.org/name
Definition:	The name of an enterprise (potentially individual but typically collaborative), planned to achieve a particular aim.
Comment:	—
Use Case:	GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal, OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary:	N/A
Value scheme:	text
Obligation:	OPTIONAL
Occurrences:	0 – 1
ConceptLink:	project name

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	—
Schema.org:	sdo:name [GDS:—]
DataCite:	—
DCAT2:	rdfs:label
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	//Session/Project/Name or //Session/Project/Title
Meta Share:	//resourceInfo/projectInfo/projectName
VLO Facet:	—
HZSK:	Project/Name or Project/Title
IDS (ADG):	//Ereignis/Projekt/@Titel
CHILDES:	—
Wikidata-Property:	project (Q170584)

ProjectDescription

Label:	ProjectName
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URI: <https://schema.org/Project>
Definition: The description of an enterprise (potentially individual but typically collaborative), planned to achieve a particular aim.
Comment: —
Use Case: GDS/Schema.org, Citation, Legal, OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: text
Obligation: OPTIONAL
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: [description](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: —
DC Terms: —
Schema.org: [sdo:description](#) [GDS:—]
DataCite: —
DCAT2: —
OLAC: —
IMDI Element: //Session/Project/Description or //Session/Project/Description
Meta Share: —
VLO Facet: —
HZSK: Project/Description
IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Projekt/Anmerkungen
CHILDES: imdi:ProjectDescription
Wikidata-Property: description

Language data

Language data can occur in more than one form. Language data resources can contain primary data from one or more languages. The dataset can contain written data, but also audio or audio-visual data with or without transcripts or annotations.

Property	URI	Optionality
objectLanguage	olac:language	REQUIRED
linguisticDataType	olac:linguistic-type	RECOMMENDED
modality	imdi:modalities	RECOMMENDED

ObjectLanguage

Label: objectLanguage
URI: <http://www.language-archives.org/REC/language.html>

Definition: Language the resource is about.
Comment: In a dataset, this is the language (or one of the languages) that is spoken, signed, written or otherwise used to communicate.
Use Case: OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: component, anyURI
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – unbounded
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [dc:language](#)
DC Terms: [dcterms:language](#)
Schema.org: [sdo:language](#) [GDS:—]
DataCite: —
TEI-Header: //profileDesc/langUsage/language
DCAT2: [dcterms:language](#)
OLAC: [olac:language](#)
IMDI Element: //Session/Content/Languages/Language
Meta Share: //resourceInfo/documentInfo/documentLanguageName or
/Corpora/resourceInfo/corpusTextInfo/languageInfo
/languageName
VLO Facet: Language
HZSK: SubjectLanguage
IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Sprecherereignis/Sprachen
CHILDES: Subject.olac:language and Language
Wikidata-Property: language of work or name ([P407](#))

LinguisticDataType

Label: linguisticDataType
URI: <http://www.language-archives.org/REC/type.html>
Definition: Provides a broad classification of the nature of the resource from a linguistic point of view (namely, as a lexicon, a primary text, or a language description).
Comment: The vocabulary *lexicon, primary text, language description* is not sufficient.
Use Case: OLAC, VLO, LangDoc

Vocabulary: [lexicon, primary text and language description](#)
Value scheme: text
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – unbounded
ConceptLink: [resource type](#)

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	(dc:type)
DC Terms:	(dcterms:type)
Schema.org:	[GDS:—]
DataCite:	—
TEI-Header:	—
DCAT2:	—
OLAC:	olac:linguistic-type
IMDI Element:	—
Meta Share:	—
VLO Facet:	Resource type
HZSK:	—
IDS (ADG):	—
CHILDES:	Type.olac:linguistic-type
Wikidata-Property:	—

Modality

Label:	modality
URI:	—
Definition:	The channel by which communication in the resource is transmitted.
Comment:	Typical values are <i>spoken</i> , <i>signed</i> , <i>written</i>
Use Case:	OLAC, VLO, LangDoc

Vocabulary:	Open vocabulary list
Value scheme:	text
Obligation:	RECOMMENDED
Occurrences:	0 – unbounded
ConceptLink:	—

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	—
DC Terms:	—
Schema.org:	— [GDS:—]
DataCite:	—
TEI-Header:	—
DCAT2:	—
OLAC:	—
IMDI Element:	//Session/Content/Modalities
Meta Share:	//Corpora/resourceInfo/corpusTextInfo/modalityInfo/modalityType
VLO Facet:	Modality
HZSK:	ModalityInfo
IDS (ADG):	—
CHILDES:	IMDI_Modalities
Wikidata-Property:	—

Language

Property	URI	Optionality
name	sdo:name	REQUIRED
preferredLabel	skos:prefLabel	RECOMMENDED
identifier	sdo:identifier	REQUIRED

Name

Label: name
URI: <https://schema.org/name>
Definition: Language name.
Comment: —
Use Case: OLAC, VLO, LangDoc

Vocabulary: N/A
Value scheme: text
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [dc:language](#)
 DC Terms: [dcterms:language](#)
 Schema.org: [sdo:name](#) [GDS:—]
 DataCite: —
 TEI-Header: //profileDesc/langUsage/language OR
 //profileDesc/langUsage/language/lang
 DCAT2: [dcterms:language](#)
 OLAC: [olac:language](#)
 IMDI Element: Content.Languages.Language
 Meta Share: //resourceInfo/documentInfo/documentLanguageName or
 //Corpora/resourceInfo/corpusTextInfo/languageInfo
 /languageName
 VLO Facet: Language
 HZSK: Language
 IDS (ADG): //Ereignis/Sprecherereignis/Sprachen
 CHILDES: Language
 Wikidata-Property: language of work or name ([P407](#))

PreferredLabel

Label: preferredLabel
URI: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel>
Definition: The preferred label as provided by an authority such as Glottolog.
Comment: —
Use Case: OLAC, VLO, LangDoc

Vocabulary: Glottolog rdfs:label
Value scheme: text, date, anyURI
Obligation: RECOMMENDED
Occurrences: 0 – 1
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements: [dc:language](#)
DC Terms: [dcterms:language](#)
Schema.org: [sdo:name](#) [GDS:—]
DataCite: —
TEI-Header: —
DCAT2: [dcterms:language](#)
OLAC: [olac:language](#)
IMDI Element: //Content/Languages/Language
Meta Share: (/Corpora/resourceInfo/corpusTextInfo/languageInfo
/languageVarietyName)
VLO Facet: Language
HZSK: —
IDS (ADG): —
CHILDES: —
Wikidata-Property: language of work or name ([P407](#))

identifier

Label: identifier
URI: sdo:identifier
Definition: A code that uniquely identifies the macrolanguage or variety it refers to.
Comment: Refinement of the sdo:identifier (similar to olac:language) containing ISO 639-3 codes or Glottocode.
Use Case: OLAC, VLO, LOD, LangDoc

Vocabulary: ISO 639-3, Glottocode
Value scheme: anyURI
Obligation: REQUIRED
Occurrences: 1 – unbounded
ConceptLink: —

(Practical) Equivalencies:

DC Elements:	dc:language
DC Terms:	dcterms:language
Schema.org:	sdo:inLanguage [GDS:—]
DataCite:	[mandatory/recommended/optional]
TEI-Header:	//profileDesc/langUsage/language/@ident or idno
DCAT2:	dcterms:language
OLAC:	olac:language
IMDI Element:	//Content/Languages/Language/Id
Meta Share:	//Corpora/resourceInfo/corpusTextInfo/languageInfo/languageId
VLO Facet:	languageCode
HZSK:	ISO639
IDS (ADG):	—
CHILDES:	Subject.olac:language
Wikidata-Property:	ISO 639-3 code (P220), Glottolog code (P1394)

Glossary

Catalog	A type of collection that describes, and points to features of another collection. (Source: https://casrai.org/term/catalogue/)
Metadata	Literally, “data about data”; data that defines and describes the characteristics of other data, used to improve both business and technical understanding of data and data-related processes. (Source: https://casrai-test.evision.ca/glossary-term/metadata/)
Catalog Metadata	
Research data	Data that are used as primary sources to support technical or scientific enquiry, research, scholarship, or artistic activity, and that are used as evidence in the research process and/or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results. All other digital and non-digital content have the potential of becoming research data. Research data may be experimental data, observational data, operational data, third party data, public sector data, monitoring data, processed data, or repurposed data. (Source:

<https://casrai-test.evision.ca/glossary-term/research-data/>)

Paradata

The paradata of a data set or survey are data about the process by which the data were collected.

(Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paradata>)

The term *paradata* refers to auxiliary data collected in a survey that describe the data collection process.

(Source:

<https://www.surveypractice.org/article/3036-paradata-in-survey-research>)

Serialization

Serialization is the process of translating a data structure or object state into a format that can be stored, (e.g. in a file) or transmitted (e.g. over a computer network) and reconstructed later in a different computer environment.

(Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Serialization>)

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